

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Hamilton**FIRST NAME:** Ertenisa**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

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QUIZ FOR COURSE PHGH ACA-401D

1. Punctuation is an integral part of academic writing and, when used inappropriately, can change the context of a sentence or paragraph. The WHO writing style outlines the rules governing the most commonly used punctuation. The below rules govern the period most commonly used except?¹
- The period is placed at the end of a sentence
 - The period is used after the initials of someone's name
 - The period is used in captions, labels, and headings *
 - For sentences that end with an abbreviation, only one period is used

¹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (Geneva: WHO, 2013), 31.

2. WHO is an organization committed to ensuring equity and respect for the fundamental human rights of every individual. As such, specific rules in writing ensure that the language used is non-discriminatory. Which of the below statements would be considered discriminatory when applying the WHO style?²

- When addressing topics of the elderly, terms such as frail, burden to society, and dependent should not be used to describe this population
- Gender-neutral language is preferred in texts contained in WHO documents
- Words such as handicapped, disabled are considered appropriate when describing a disabled person in a text *
- The racial or cultural background of an individual should only be mentioned when the subject demands it

3. The appendix of a dissertation contains copies of the resources used in the research and can be helpful for other researchers who may want to replicate the study. This section contains all of the following components except?³

- Limitations*
- Consent form
- Permission letters to use copyright information
- Raw data analyzed in a qualitative dissertation

² WHO, 55–56.

³ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 89.

4. The knowledge gained from the research findings influences the implications of the research. All of the below mentioned are implications except?⁴

- Implications for practice
- Implications for the private sector*
- Implications for education and training
- Implications for policy

5. Plagiarism is one of the practices that is frowned upon in the academic world because it gives credit to someone who did not earn it. There are many instances where plagiarism can be committed through ignorance. There are many ways to cite and quote the work of other researchers and authors to avoid this pitfall, such as paraphrasing. All of the below are true about paraphrasing except?⁵

- It must be YOUR own words.
- The writing style used to express the author's ideas must be the same as the work that is cited*
- The information provided must be an accurate representation of the original work.
- There must be a citation of where the work used originated from

6. It is recommended that a doctoral candidate, at the beginning of the dissertation planning process, select a dissertation committee that will provide oversight to the

⁴ Sampson Jr., 62.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1, Fourth edition* (Bangui: Central African Republic, 2021), 35.

candidate. The committee must be led by a sponsor, chair, or advisor who must possess all the following qualities except?⁶

- Expertise in the topic area or the discipline
- External connections to allow the candidate access to data collection*
- Access and availability of the individual by the candidate
- Understanding the process and what it takes to motivate the candidate to produce good work

7. A dissertation's methodology and research approach describe the process used to arrive at the answer to the research question. It must contain the following components.

Which of the following must be included?⁷

- Rationale for the research design
- Research population, sample, and setting
- Data collection methods and tools
- Summary*

8. Academic writing dictates that your points of view and arguments must be supported by reliable evidence. The sources of evidence used are classified as primary, secondary,

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: Sage Publications Inc, 2019), 103.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 80.

or tertiary. Identify from the list below the most accurate definition of a primary data source.⁸

- Books, articles, and reports based on previously published work mainly for use by professionals
- Books and articles that summarize secondary sources of information for a general audience
- Evidence synthesis used to effect policies
- Original materials that have raw data that is used to generate evidence*

9. The researcher's curiosity or passion drives research projects, although most share common objectives. Which of the following is not an objective of a research project?⁹

- Ask a question worth answering.
- Find an answer that you can support with good reasons.
- Write an abstract that meets international standards *
- Find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons.

10. The body of an essay is a crucial component, as it houses the bulk of the information.

Can you identify which of the following is not typically found in the body of an essay?¹⁰

- A summary or roadmap of the essay *
- Relevant examples and authoritative quotes

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Revised by Wayne Booth et al., (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

⁹ Turabian, 23.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 10.

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- Evidence to support the point of view of the writer
- An answer to the question or problem proposed in the introduction

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: Sage Publications Inc, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Bangui: Central African Republic, 2021.

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